

LATIN LANGUAGE AND DENTAL TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation. This article presents the results of the study of clinical terminology in the course of the discipline "Latin". The analysis made it possible to identify the main thematic groups of clinical terms used in the field of dentistry. The identified classification of terms is enriched with words of Greek-Latin origin, which indicates the importance of studying Latin as a language of professional communication. Key words: clinical terminology, dentistry, Latin.

Keywords. Clinical terminology / dentistry / Latin / language

Modern requirements for specialists in various fields of knowledge require a deep knowledge of the terminology of the future profession, which is especially important for medicine in general, and for dentistry in particular.

When mastering the discipline "Latin", students of the Faculty of Dentistry study medical terminology, which is a huge layer of terms denoting the concepts of medicine as a science, and the main nomenclature systems, presented in the form of terms for anatomy, histology, physiology, clinic and pharmacy.

Of particular interest is clinical terminology, as one of the most extensive and complex systems of terms in terms of concepts and content. Clinical terminology includes the names of various diseases, symptoms and signs of the disease, violations of physiological functions, structural changes in organs and tissues, as well as methods of research, treatment and prevention. In the process of studying clinical terminology, future dentists master a huge number of clinical terms borrowed from Latin and Greek. It is important to know that when translating such terms are transliterated into Cyrillic, adapting their endings to fit into the Russian system of declensions. Clinical terms differ in their structure: they can be simple, derivative (affixal) and complex. However, a deep analysis of clinical terminology gave reason to single out the following main thematic groups of clinical terms used in the field of dentistry.

1) Terms that name the clinical symptoms of diseases. This thematic group includes terms denoting signs of the disease, i.e. indicating a deviation from the norm: odontalgia (odontalgia) - toothache; hyperaesthesia (hyperesthesia) - increased sensitivity of hard dental tissues; odontolithus (odontolith) - plaque

on the teeth, tartar; ulorrhagia (ulorrhagia) - bleeding from the gums; halitosis (halitosis) - bad breath, etc.

The largest number of terminological units of this thematic group is complex terms, consisting of terminological elements of Greek origin.

2) Terms used as names of dental diseases: caries (caries) - a disease in which the hard tissues of the tooth are destroyed with the formation of a cavity; gingivitis (gingivitis) - inflammation of the gums, which is characterized by bleeding and swelling of the gums. For the names of dental diseases, simple or derived clinical terms are more often used. Simple clinical terms are words of Latin or Greek origin, which, within the framework of clinical terminology, are morphologically indivisible: abscessus (abscess) - abscess, abscess. Derived clinical terms are characterized by the presence of a suffix or prefix that carry certain information. Having incorrectly formed a word when designating a pathology, a dentist can make an inaccuracy in the diagnosis, since in clinical terms affixes have a specific meaning. The most common formants in clinical terminology are:

- suffix -itis, which formed a microsystem of names for inflammatory diseases: alveolitis (alveolitis) - inflammation of the tooth socket, usually due to infection of the wound at the time or after tooth extraction; cheilitis (cheilitis) - inflammation of the lips, glossitis (glossitis) - acute or chronic inflammation of the tongue. Prefixes also perform a semantic function: parodontitis (periodontitis) is an inflammatory periodontal disease that occurs with the destruction of the dentogingival junction and interalveolar septa. If the integumentary membrane of the organ is affected by inflammation, the prefix peri-periodontitis (periodontitis) is added to the clinical term - inflammation of the root shell of the tooth (periodontium); periostitis (periostitis) - inflammation of the periosteum of the jaw in the form of swelling of the gums near the diseased tooth;

- the suffix -ōma, attached to the basis of the name of the tissue, forms the names of tumors that arise from this tissue: paradontoma (paradontoma) - tumor and tumor-like disease of the periodontium; cementoma (cementoma) - benign tumor, tissue structure resembles a whole tooth;

- suffix -ōsis with the meaning "process or its result"; concrementosis (concrementosis) - the formation of pathological seals; with the meaning "chronic degenerative disease of the organ"; fluorosis- (fluorosis) is a chronic disease caused by excessive intake of fluorine into the body.

3) Terms denoting methods of diagnosis and treatment. This group, as a rule, is represented by borrowed complex terms, which include term elements of Greek origin -graphia, -metria, -scopia, -therapia. For example, orthopantomography (orthopantomography) is a method of radiography in which an image of both jaws and maxillary joints, as well as the maxillary sinuses, is obtained on one overview (panaromic) image; antibioticotherapia (antibiotic therapy) - treatment with antibiotics; electroodontometria (electroodontometry) - measurement of tooth reactions to electric current, etc.

Thus, as can be seen from the above classification, clinical terminology in dentistry is enriched with words of Greek-Latin origin. This allows us to conclude that the study of clinical terminology in the course of the discipline "Latin" for students of the Faculty of Dentistry is the main component of medical culture, and the ability to use it adequately acts as the language of professional communication.

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